

Design and simulation hybrid filter for 17 level multilevel inverter

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ABSTRACT

The increasing of renewable energy applications such as solar cells, wind power, ocean thermal and HVDC (high voltage direct current) cause increment in the use of the inverter circuit. Harmonics that are generated by the inverter have negative impacts on the electrical equipment; harmonics cause excessive heat and may shorten the life of electrical equipment. A multilevel inverter is an arranged of cascaded inverters which aims to reduce total harmonic distortion (THD). This paper proposes the design of 17 levels of a single-phase cascaded multilevel inverter with a hybrid filter insertion. By using PSIM simulator, the hybrid filter is proven reducing THD better than single pulse width modulation (SPWM) inverter. Installation of the hybrid filter is able to fix a maximum of 0.23% THD_v and a maximum of 1.05% THD_i. Hybrid filter installation reduces the value of THD to comply with IEEE 519-2014 standard.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Population increases every year. This growth is directly proportional to the need for electrical energy, which is also growing [1]. As energy sources are limited, the use of renewable energy becomes an alternative to satisfy the need for electrical energy. Since electrical waveform generated by renewable sources such as solar cells is dominated by direct current (DC), the used of inverter becomes frequent to convert DC Voltage to AC Voltage. Such devices have been widely available in the market and have been used for many applications [2]. However, the AC waveform generated by the inverters is often costly, poor quality output and containing high harmonic indices [3]. Many researchers have done real works in designing inverter. For instance, Arif et al [4] focused on the multi-level topology, while Jidin et al [5] used space vector modulation to improve the output voltage. Another researcher [6] reduced the total harmonics distortion (THD) by adjusting the inverter itself. Therefore, this paper focuses on the use of filters in inverter. This paper proposes a hybrid filter insertion on the output of the inverter. It is expected by doing so, THD complies with the IEEE 519-2014 standard requirement [7]. The proposed filter is a hybrid filter, which is a combination of two filters: an active filter and a passive filter [8, 9]. Hybrid filters have more benefits than passive filters in filtering harmonics, both from the viewpoint of usefulness and performance, particularly for extraordinary power applications [10, 11].

The active filter is delineated by performing similar to resistors during harmonic frequencies, resulting in harmonic elimination across distribution channels [12]. The active filter works by injecting harmonic current into the circuit so the inverter can work under different load conditions. It is applied to

compensate voltage harmonic in series with active power filter or to compensate current harmonic in shunt with active power filter [13, 14]. The active filter injects the compensation current into the circuit. Therefore, the THDi in the circuit improves. The passive filter works on a particular tuned frequency so that harmonic current is passed through a passive filter and the load receives voltage and current with muted harmonics.

The LCL filter is a popular solution for voltage source converter connected to the network for its ability to achieve better harmonic switching mitigation [15-17]. Previously, the L filter was used to reduce the harmonic content at high switching frequencies, by inserting it in between the grid source and the converter's poles [18, 19]. However, to meet the power quality standard, a significant value of inductor is expected [20]. Thirumoorthi & Yadaiah state that LC filter is the simplest method to mitigate the reactive power and harmonic current [21]. Nevertheless, its simple approach also has limitations [22]. Therefore, to gain maximum results, the LCL filter is installed as a passive filter in this work.

The IEEE 519-2014 allows the permitted THD level by a maximum value of 8%. THD level higher than 8% may generate non-sinusoidal output that injects negative influences on the loads. High harmonic values increase the temperature of electronic devices, which become rapidly hot. The manual pulse settings cause unstable generated frequencies [23].

2. CASCADED MULTILEVEL INVERTER

The output voltage generated by the inverter is ideally sinusoidal [24]. However, in reality, it contains harmonics that generate non-sinusoidal output waveform. The non-sinusoidal transients are still acceptable for low and medium power applications. Nevertheless, minimal inverter requirements for harmonics and sinusoidal voltages are needed for high power applications [25].

Figure 1 shows three different inverter output voltages: + VDC, 0 and -VDC. DC source is connected to the AC output side by various combinations of four switches: S1, S2, S3, and S4. For instance, by turning ON S1 and S4 yield + VDC, turning ON S2 and S3 yield -VDC and turning OFF all switches yield 0 voltage. The output voltage is the sum of the voltages generated by each inverter level. The output voltage level is $2n + 1$, where n is the number of DC voltage sources.

Figure 1. Cascaded multilevel inverter, (a) Inverter circuit, (b) Output waveform

Since the inverter has five DC sources, the output voltage level will be 11 levels of cascaded multilevel inverter. The higher the levels, the better the quality of the output [26]. The first H-bridge produces VDC1 Volt during time Θ_1 . The second H-bridge provides VDC2 Volt during time Θ_2 and so on until VDC5. The sum of the five inverter outputs synthesizes the phase output voltage, $V_{Out}=VDC1+VDC2+VDC3+VDC4+VDC5$, as expressed by (1) [1], where $V(\omega t)$ is the output voltage, VDC is DC input voltage source and θ is IGBT turning point.

$$V_{(\omega t)} = \frac{4V_{DC}}{n\pi} \sum_{n=1,3,5,\dots}^{\infty} [Cos(n\theta_1) + Cos(n\theta_2) + \dots + Cos(n\theta_n)] Sin(n\omega t) \quad (1)$$

3. CIRCUIT DESIGN

3.1. Design 17 level cascaded multilevel inverter

The multilevel inverter cascaded circuit uses 8 H-bridge inverters. Each level works on 30 VDC voltages. Each H-bridge inverter uses four pieces insulated gate bipolar transistors (IGBTs). IGBT is a semiconductor component that is widely used as a switch that combines high-efficiency switching [27]. IGBT is a transistor that designed with high impedance, so it does not overload the control circuit, especially the driver part. Different from any previous power semiconductors, the ON and OFF conditions of IGBT do not produce power losses.

The working pulse/angle setting of IGBT uses a pulse generator. In PSIM software simulator, this setting is available by using a gating block for the switch. Gating block switch 1 (G1) is used for IGBT 1 and 4 drivers. Gating block switch 2 (G2) is used as IGBT 2 and IGBT 3. The G1 driver is set at the ignition angle from 5° to 175° for positive pulses. G2 is set on the ignition angle from 185° to 355° for negative pulses. Setup for all drivers is displayed in Table 1.

After adjusting all gating blocks as described in Table 1, the voltage probe is added to evaluate the waveform generated by the cascaded multilevel inverter circuit. The whole circuit of the multilevel cascaded inverter is shown in Figure 2. The designed circuit is assembled by 32 IGBTs, connected to 8 voltage source of 30 VDC. After simulation executed, the output voltage generated by this circuit and its THD values are obtained. Figure 3 shows the waveforms and harmonics spectrum of the output voltage. The effective root mean square (rms) value of the output voltage (V_{rms}) is 153.49 V and the total harmonic distortion (THD_v) produced by this circuit is 11.72%.

Table 1. Setting IGBT ignition angle

Gating Block	IGBT	Ignition Angle ($^\circ$)
G1	1 & 4	5-175
G2	2 & 3	185-355
G3	5 & 8	15-165
G4	6 & 7	195-345
G5	9 & 12	25-155
G6	10 & 11	205-335
G7	13 & 16	35-145
G8	14 & 15	215-325
G9	17 & 20	45-135
G10	18 & 19	225-315
G11	29 & 32	55-125
G12	30 & 31	235-305
G13	26 & 27	245-295
G14	25 & 28	65-115
G15	22 & 23	255-285
G16	21 & 24	75-105

3.2. Filter design

The source impedance strongly affect the filtering characteristics. It causes system resonance in passive filter application. These drawbacks can be removed by introducing a combination of active and passive power filters with appropriate coordination. The LCL passive filter is used in design due to its high filtering performance. LCL filter minimizes cost, size and weight. Moreover, LCL filter is suitable to meet harmonic constraints as defined by standard IEEE 519 [28]. The designed active filter control is performed by using current sensors, summing amplifiers and inverting amplifiers. The current sensor detects the changing current and transmits its waveforms to the summing amplifier. The current waveform

is a reference wave to be compared to the sine waveform generated by the oscillator. The comparison result is the current waveform that is injected into the circuit as compensation.

The inverting amplifier circuit serves as a voltage inverter for the phase voltage generated by a sine wave oscillator. This sine wave is 180° phase different from the sine wave generated by the oscillator. The inverting amplifier circuit adjusts the IGBT startup angle and the summing amplifier circuit controls the compensation current. The active filter used in this work is an active shunt filter. The topology is depicted in Figure 4. Input filter is taken from the driver inverter, and the output filter is connected to the load. The active shunt filter injects the compensation current into the circuit so that the THDi value in the injected circuit improves.

Figure 2. The multilevel inverter simulation circuit

The active shunt filter uses a voltage source inverter (VSI) and the inverter type is the H-bridge inverter. The H-bridge inverter is driven by the generated harmonics. The SPWM generator is used to ignite the IGBTs. The single-phase full-bridge inverter is arranged in series of sinus generators (oscillators). The output is then compared to the output waveform of the summing amplifier. Afterward, the current injection flows through the Lf inductor. The driver and the compensation circuits are shown in Figure 5.

The LCL filter circuit design is shown in Figure 6. The value of C is determined based on values 0.0001F or 100µF. The cutoff frequency is determined 50 Hz as the power frequency of the intended application. Then inductor value, L is determined by using (2) [1].

$$f_{cut\ off} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{L_1 + L_2}{L_1 \cdot L_2 \cdot C}} \tag{2}$$

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. Output voltage waveform and its harmonic spectrum, (a) Voltage waveform, (b) Harmonic spectrum

Figure 4. Block diagram of the active filter

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. Driver series of IGBT SPWM one phase inverter, (a) Driver circuit, (b) Injection current

Figure 6. LCL filter

4. CIRCUIT TESTING

The multilevel inverter cascaded circuit is tested by using linear load and non-linear load. Linear load uses a resistor, while non-linear load uses RL load, a step-up transformer and a single-phase full-bridge converter. Load test parameters are plotted in Table 2. The linear load is made of a 12 Ω. This value is selected to avoid over current flows in the designed circuit. The RL non-linear load is by using a 12 Ω resistor and a 10 mH inductor. The transformer load is an asymmetric primary and secondary turns (step-up). Finally, the full bridge converter is also connected to 12 Ω resistor.

The overall circuit blocks are depicted in Figure 7. The cascaded multilevel inverter is arranged in parallel to the active filter and the passive filter and is arranged in series to the cascaded multilevel inverter. After the circuits have been arranged, the load is connected to the circuit.

Table 2. Load test parameters

Type of load	Value of load
R Load	$R=12\Omega$
R-L Load	$R=12\Omega$ and $L=10\text{mH}$
Transformer Load	$N_p=200$ and $N_s=400$
Full bridge converter load	$R=12\Omega$

Figure 7. The overall circuit block

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

5.1. Test results for non-filter inverter

Test results without filter are plotted in Table 3. The waveforms are shown in Figure 8. THDv and THDi are generated higher than the permitted levels of IEEE 519-2014 which mean higher than the allowed value of 8%. The test without filter produce THDv of 59.46% and THDi 59.46% for resistive load. The RL load causes higher THDv of 65.74% and lower THDi 51.59%. Trafo step up generates lower THD than resistive load, while the converter provides lower THDv but similar THDi to resistive load.

Table 3. Test results for non-filter inverter

No	Type of load	THDv	THDi
1	R	59.46%	59.46%
2	RL	65.74%	51.59%
3	Trafo step up	58.55%	58.14%
4	Full bridge converter	59.34%	59.46%

Figure 8. Non-filter test results, (a) R load, (b) RL load, (c) Step-up transformer load, (d) Converter load

5.2. Test results for hybrid filter inverter

The multilevel inverter cascaded circuit is coupled with a hybrid filter and then connected to the same load as previous test. The generated waveforms can be seen in Figure 9. The THD values are at the permitted levels of IEEE 519-2014. The generated waveforms after filtering become sinusoidal.

Figure 9. Test results for hybrid filter, (a) R load, (b) RL load, (c) Step up transformer load, (d) Converter load

The test results with hybrid filter installed produce THD_v of 0.09% and THD_i 0.09% for resistive load. The RL load produces higher THD_v of 0.11% and THD_i of 0.10%. Trafo step up generates higher THD than R load, while the converter provides higher THD_v but similar THD_i to R load. These values are plotted in Table 4.

Table 4. Test results using the hybrid filter

No	Type of load	Filter Hybrid	
		THDv	THDi
1	R	0.09%	0.09%
2	RL	0.11%	0.10%
3	Trafo Step Up	0.23%	1.05%
4	Converter	0.10%	0.09%

5.3. Discussion

Simulations results show that the output waveforms of the inverter without filter are mostly non-sinusoidal with high THD values (as shown in Table 3). By adding filter, the output waveforms become sinusoidal with much lower THD values (as shown in Table 4). THDv and THDi of the inverter with filter are still within the permitted level of IEEE 519-2014 which are maximum THDv is 0.1% and maximum THDi is 1.05%. The hybrid filter is significantly reducing the output harmonics up to 65.63%.

On the other hand, filter addition to the inverter circuit causes transient phenomenon. Transient causes output amplitude require sometime to reach typical amplitude value. It is different from non-filter inverter that produces maximum amplitude from the beginning circuit turned on. Inductor and capacitor in filter delayed the amplitude rise. Transient process occurs as inductor and capacitor made energy exchanges. Step transformer load requires about 0.4 s to reach maximum amplitude, while resistive load requires the shortest one, less than 0.2 s.

6. CONCLUSION

Power quality has become necessary since the renewable energy becomes circulating in the market. Since renewable energy sources are dominated by DC voltage, the inverter becomes an important device. This paper has proposed a hybrid filter insertion to the multilevel cascaded inverter to reduce voltage and current harmonics. The assessments using PSIM simulator show that the effectiveness of proposed multilevel cascaded 17 level inverter with hybrid filter for four different load types. The filter is able to reduce the THDv and THDi up to 65.63%. The active filter injected the compensation current into the circuit and the LCL filter absorbed the harmonics that occur over the 50 HZ frequency, so that the resulting harmonics are still within the permitted level of IEEE 519-2014. On the other hand, filter drawback on the inverter output is injecting additional transient time to reach maximum amplitude as capacitor and inductor exchanges energy during filtering. Even though, the output voltage is relatively stable as transient over.

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